

FEATURES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN IN A BILINGUAL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. *The term bilingualism here suggests the acquisition of two languages during the first six years of life. This definition includes the following conditions: (a) Children are able to comprehend and/or produce linguistic aspects of two languages. (b) Children are exposed "naturally" to the two systems of languages as they are used in the form of social interaction during early childhood. This condition requires a substantive bilingual environment. In many cases this exposure comes from within a nuclear and extended family network but this need not be the case (visitors, and extended visits to foreign countries are examples of alternative environments). (c) The simultaneous character of development must be apparent in both languages. This is contrasted with the case of a native speaker of one language, who after mastery of that language, begins on a course of second language acquisition. It is the preceding combined conditions which define the present population of interest. It is clear from this definition that an attempt is made to include the child's linguistic abilities in conjunction with the social environment during an important "developmental segment" of life and at the time of learning second language.*

Key words: *social and cultural, environment, bilingualism, kindergarten.*

ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАЗВИТИЯ ДОШКОЛЬНИКОВ В БИЯЗЫЧНОЙ СРЕДЕ

Аннотация. *Термин билингвизм здесь предполагает овладение двумя языками в течение первых шести лет жизни. Это определение включает следующие условия: (а) Дети способны понимать и/или воспроизводить лингвистические аспекты двух языков. (б) Дети «естественно» знакомятся с двумя системами языков, поскольку они используются в форме социального взаимодействия в раннем детстве. Это условие требует существенной двуязычной среды. Во многих случаях такое воздействие происходит внутри нуклеарной и расширенной семейной сети, но это не обязательно (посетители и продолжительные визиты в зарубежные страны являются примерами альтернативной среды). (с) Одновременный характер развития должен быть очевиден в обоих языках. Это контрастирует со случаем носителя одного языка, который после овладения этим языком начинает курс овладения вторым языком. Это предшествующие комбинированные условия, которые определяют нынешнюю интересующую совокупность. Из этого определения ясно, что делается попытка включить языковые способности ребенка во взаимосвязь с социальной средой на важном «развивающем отрезке» жизни и во время изучения второго языка.*

Ключевые слова: *социокультурная среда, билингвизм, детский сад.*

INTRODUCTION

Modern requirements for the organization of the educational process are dictated by changes in the political, social and cultural spheres of society. The focus is on the personality

and interests of the student, his creative and cognitive potential. Changes in early language education are especially dynamic. Changes in the requirements for the quality of knowledge of an international language like English led to the search for the most optimal approaches to the early development of a foreign language. The education system faced the task of preparing a multifaceted intellectual personality who is fluent in native and foreign languages from the preschool age.

In the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated May 19, 2021 No. DP-5117 "On measures to raise to a qualitatively new level of activities to promote the study of foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan", the task was set to establish an Agency for the Promotion of the Study of Foreign Languages under the Cabinet of Ministers and positions of regional representatives of the Agency in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and the city of Tashkent. Determine the main tasks of the Agency: coordination of the development of language learning methods and recommendations suitable for all categories of the population in order to introduce the chain of continuous education into the field of teaching foreign languages according to the principle "**kindergarten** - school - higher educational organization - enterprise"; where pre-school educational institutions are the first and important stage. The introduction of a foreign language has an effective development not only for the development of the country, but also for the development of the child.

The topic of the influence of bilingual education on the development of a child is considered in all modern research literature. At different times, performance indicators, language acquisition, and general mastery of the program were singled out as performance criteria, which revealed only such an aspect of the problem as the quality of bilingual educational programs. However, an equally important aspect is the issue of the comprehensive development of bilingual preschool children.

In the scientific community, more and more attention is paid to the issue of assessing the intellectual abilities and the level of formation of cognitive skills in bilingual children. With the development of bilingual methods, the thesis about the cognitive development of bilinguals is increasingly confirmed, which makes bilingual education in preschool educational institutions attractive not only from the point of view of mastering a second language in a sensitive period, but also from the point of view of creating conditions for its intellectual development. Another equally important positive impact of development in a bilingual environment for young children is speech development.

Most researchers (A.A. Leontiev, E.I. Negnevitskaya, N.D. Galskova, Z.N. Nikitenko) associate the beginning of a child's development when mastering a foreign language with the following points: with the child's readiness for conscious learning, the formation of language and speech mechanisms of the native language, with susceptibility to a new language (this age is determined by 5-6 years). However, the data of many studies suggest that the acquisition of a second language is possible at an earlier age when the child is immersed in the language environment, which is the basis for the upbringing and development of the child.

MAIN PART

It is known that preschool education, including bilingual education, aims to satisfy the cognitive, playful, personal, psychophysiological needs and abilities of the child and must comply with the principles of developmental education and integration, the abilities and characteristics of pupils, etc. Education of preschoolers in two languages becomes possible in

line with the ontolinguistic, environmental and communicative-cognitive approaches at the initial stage of education. In the psycholinguistics of preschool education (I.A. Zimnyaya, A.A. Leontiev), communicative activity is considered as an activity of communication and involves the ability to correctly and quickly navigate in communication conditions and plan speech, and choose content communication, find and apply adequate language means in order to convey thoughts and provide feedback. The bilingual educational environment in a preschool educational institution implies the ability to use the entire range of development and upbringing tools that stimulate the child's speech activity in their native and foreign languages, which allows him, by the end of mastering the preschool program, not only to use two languages for educational and domestic purposes, but also effectively affects development.

The postulates of cognitive psychology are also an actual area of study for designing the developmental features of preschoolers in a bilingual environment. Founded in the late 1950s and early 1960s. (Bodalev A.A., Velichkovsky B.M., Kovale G.A., Piaget J., Solso R., Bruner G., Miller G., etc.), it served as a scientific basis for many teaching methods from an early age.

The objects of research on the features of cognitive development are cognitive processes, such as aspects of speech and language, representation of information, memory, logical thinking, cognitive abilities, etc. In education, cognitive development is commonly understood as development that relies on the cognitive development of the student. Foreign scientists (P.R. Goodenough, G. Lakoff, R. Langaker, A.Zh. Silverman, etc.) and domestic scientists (I.L. Beam, A.D. Deikina, E. S. Kubryakov, A. A. Leontiev, O. G. Malaya, A. N. Shamov, A. V. Shchepilova, etc.). Linguistics at an early preschool age focused on the analysis of processes associated with the perception, comprehension, and knowledge of reality. Research in this area makes it possible to draw conclusions about the cognitive potential of language acquisition, to develop methods for assessing the intellectual development of bilingual children and the potential of curricula in preschool educational institutions

The study of the current situation in the field of bilingual education made it possible to identify contradictions between:

1. Increasing requirements for the level of foreign language communicative and cognitive ability of children and the impossibility of natural learning of a foreign language in a sensitive period.
2. Speech, intellectual and cognitive development of the child through the development of a second foreign language at an early age and the lack of sufficiently scientifically based methods in the field of organizing preschool education in a foreign language.

The above contradictions required the determination of the most suitable conditions for the development of a preschooler in a bilingual environment and the identification of features in the development of children by creating a bilingual educational and developmental environment and experimental testing of its effectiveness in the development of a child.

The effectiveness criteria were the level of formation and communicative skills and cognitive abilities of preschool children in the process of learning and development in a bilingual environment in preschool educational institutions.

For a long time, researchers of the development of the cognitive process in children in a bilingual environment have discussed the issue of the disadvantages and advantages of bilingual development. The ontogeny of children's speech in a bilingual educational environment

(upbringing and / or education) raises a large number of questions related to the assessment of the intellectual development of bilingual children.

In the 20-30s of the twentieth century, most researchers came to the conclusion about the negative impact of bilingualism on the intellectual development of the child. Researchers of this phenomenon have noted that bilingual children who are mastering primary and secondary school programs have lowered IQ and even mental retardation. In these studies, the term "speech inferiority" was often used to explain the reasons for the academic failure of children.

In the 30s of the twentieth century, during the period of negative assessments of bilingualism, L.S. Vygotsky suggested that multilingualism can have a positive effect on thinking and the level of human development. He argued that the ability to express thoughts in spirit and more languages allows the child to look at his language as a certain system, thus giving rise to the consciousness of linguistic operations. During such operations, a person simultaneously uses two different sign systems, and sometimes more.

Among the distinguished cognitive superiority, researchers of the 70-80s noted the following abilities:

- To generalizing conclusions (Liedtke, Nelson, 1986)
- Towards the solution of problems related to verbal transformation and replacement (Ekstrand, 1980)
- Towards the use of complex analytical strategies in solving non-verbal problems (Ben-Zeev, 1977)

Flexibility of thinking and the ability to work with semantically different information of different levels were recognized as specific features of the cognitive sphere of bilingual children.

For the first time, types of thinking were described by the American psychologist Joy Paul Gilford. The scientist identified convergent and divergent types of thinking. Convergent - habitual thinking, in which tasks are solved in stages. On the basis of this mechanism of thinking, the usual tests for the level of intelligence are carried out. Divergent thinking refers to creative thinking. People with this mindset, when solving problems, start from the problem and find several ways to solve it, discovering a whole variety of combinations of cause and effect. This type of thinking is not quantifiable. Many of its owners show an average IQ, but according to a study by L. Ricciardelli in the early 90s. it can be concluded that the thinking of a bilingual child has considerable flexibility.

Kessler, C. Quinn (1987) drew attention to the fact that bilingual children often use metaphors and complex syntactic constructions in speech. It is common for such children to put forward hypotheses and stand up for their confirmation, creating new language constructions.

The advantage of bilinguals is due to their ability in the selection and current control of stimuli: the ability to choose what matters in a given context. In the case of variable use of languages, they must, according to the situation, activate one of them and suppress the other. For someone who grows up learning two languages at the same time, such transitions occur naturally. These children develop more flexible language acquisition strategies from birth. The brain of a bilingual child distinguishes between stimuli coming from different linguistic systems. Teaching a child in two languages supports the development of his cognitive and extralinguistic abilities at a high level.

CONCLUSION

The positive influence of bilingualism on the development of the child can be considered proven. All of the above allows us to assert the importance of creating a bilingual educational developmental environment in a preschool institution for the purposes of intellectual and communicative-cognitive development of children. This need is also dictated by the socio-cultural conditions and value orientations of preschool education, fixed in state standards.

An analysis of bilingual programs developed both in Uzbekistan and abroad showed that for the most part they affect the primary level of education and only a small number implement programs in a foreign language or two languages at the level of preschool education. The key task is to design such an educational environment, which is based on an understanding of the essence of bilingual education and ideas about its positive impact on the intellectual and cognitive-communicative development of the child.

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